

HIPPARCOS / TYCHO

Hardware requirements for TYCHO data analysis

L Lindegren 1981 Sept 15

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-221 04 LUND, Sweden

1. Introduction

The computing effort for TYCHO was derived in a previous note (LL, 1981 Aug 13) from which the following summary table is drawn:

processing stage	no. of mult.	amount of data, type of access
		100,000 Mb sequential (raw data)
preprocessing	$7 \cdot 10^{12}$	
		5,000 Mb - " -
A/B coincidence	$7 \cdot 10^{11}$	
		2,000 Mb - " -
p/f coincidence	$3 \cdot 10^{10}$	
		700 Mb - " -
calculation of candidate locations	$7 \cdot 10^{10}$	
		200 Mb random
second pass	$4 \cdot 10^{11}$	
		20 Mb - " - (TYCHO Catalogue)
	<u>sum total</u> $8 \cdot 10^{12}$	

The TYCHO data analysis is naturally divided in two stages of rather different nature. The preprocessing stage is characterised by:

1. an excessive amount of input (raw) data (0.1 Tb $\approx$ 3000 mag tapes);
2. simplicity (the main process is a linear filtering);
3. purely sequential data access (no iteration loop comprising more than a few kb of input data);
4. many operations per second (at least 100,000 multiplications per second and the same number of additions for execution time $\leq$ 2.5 yr);
5. high numerical accuracy not required (16 bit integer arithmetic may be sufficient for the filtering).

The other stage, the proper processing (comprising A/B coincidence detection, p/f coincidence, calculation of candidate positions, and the second pass), has the following characteristics:

1. a moderate amount of input data (5 Gb $\approx$ 150 mag tapes);
2. complexity of algorithms;
3. random access to rather big data sets is required ($\sim$ 100 Mb);
4. the total number of arithmetic operations is substantially less than for the preprocessing;
5. high numerical accuracy is often required.

The hardware requirements are thus completely different for the two stages. The character of the preprocessing suggests that it should be performed by dedicated hardware more or less continuously as the input data come along, preferably at the ground station or operation centre (to avoid shipment of large number of tapes), possibly even on board the satellite. The proper processing is of a more 'ordinary' nature which could be carried out at a computing centre or (temporally diluted) as a major project at a smaller facility.

Only the requirements for the proper processing are considered in this note.

2. Arithmetic precision

The requirements on arithmetic precision are essentially set by the final astrometric accuracy aimed at for the TYCHO project, viz. of the order of 0.03 arcsec. To avoid significant rounding errors in the end results, the precision of the internal representation should be at least 100 times better, or 0.0003 arcsec = $2 \cdot 10^{-10}$ rev. In floating point representation this relative precision is obtained with $\geq$ 32 bit mantissa.

Another consideration is that the floating-point arithmetic should provide correct rounding. If this is not the case, the above 'safety factor' of 100 is not sufficient.

3. Arithmetic speed

The number of arithmetic operations for the proper processing was estimated by counting the total number of multiplications: $\approx 10^{12}$. Thus additions, divisions, evaluation of indices and fetching/storing data are not directly counted. There is typically about one addition per multiplication and one fetch/store cycle, while the number of divisions is much smaller. Thus we

define: (1 mul) = (1 multiplication) + (1 addition) + (2 data transfers), all operations referring to floating point numbers with ≥ 32 bit mantissa.

The total effort for the proper processing is then 10^{12} mul. It would be unreasonable if the effective computing time exceeds some 10 % of the total duration of the project (which is about 4 years); thus the requirement: 10^{12} mul $\leq 10^7$ sec, or 1 mul ≤ 10 μ s.

4. Storage capacity

Most of the proper processing is made more or less sequentially, i.e. in the same order as data are gathered by the satellite. Both input and output data at these stages can be stored on mag tapes. At a rather late stage of the reductions, however, a large number of candidate locations for TYCHO stars are produced in chronological order, but must be stored in a systematic way (according to position on the sky) for subsequent analysis. For these data, estimated to about 200 Mb, some kind of random access is required. In terms of hardware, the absolute minimum requirement seems to be a 100 Mb disc drive, although 200 - 300 Mb is probably very desirable.

There are no particular requirements on primary memory capacity.